

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

MANAGEMENT OF ONLINE CLASSES/ APPLICATION OF WEB 2.0 TECHNOLOGIES IN ONLINE CLASSES

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Abstract

The rapid shift to online education during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed significant challenges in classroom management, student engagement, and the effective use of digital tools. This study examines the main issues teachers face in online classes, including student lateness, lack of attention, technical difficulties, and behavioral problems. It also explores strategies for establishing discipline, increasing learner engagement, and organizing the virtual learning environment effectively. Special attention is given to the pedagogical role of teacher behavior, intonation, visual materials, and feedback mechanisms in sustaining student focus. Furthermore, the paper highlights the importance and pedagogical value of Web 2.0 technologies, emphasizing their ability to enhance interaction, collaboration, and access to authentic learning resources. The findings indicate that effective management of online classes requires a combination of clear rules, active communication, technological literacy, and purposeful use of interactive Web 2.0 tools to create a productive, engaging, and learner-centered online environment.

Keywords: Online classroom management; distance learning; student engagement; Web 2.0 technologies; virtual learning environment

Establishing discipline in online classes is one of the most important problems that a teacher has to solve. Of course, we all know that discipline does not mean preventing noise alone. One of the most common problems in online classes is that students join the class late. In fact, what is expected is that in online classes, since the student is at home, he does not go anywhere during breaks, and there is no reason to be late for the class when it starts. However, due to the COVID19 pandemic, we witnessed a completely different picture when classes were taught remotely... To prevent lateness to the class and to accustom students to joining the class on time, you must first join the class on time. If students see that the teacher has joined the class late several times, they will repeat this action. It is imperative to conclude all the material in the time allotted for the class. Start lessons on time and finish when the time is up. Avoid reprimanding or punishing students for being late. If you do, the student may have a good reason (excuse) to prove that the tardiness or absence was not their fault. One of the most common complaints teachers make about online classes is the difficulty of getting students to pay attention. Of course, it is not that difficult to get students to pay attention to the lesson in face-to-face classes, but it is not so easy to get the attention of students who are physically located on the other side of the screen, in different places, and who are not close to you.

How can you tell if a student sitting in front of the camera is listening to the lesson? If the student's gaze is always directed downwards (most likely, the student is writing, doing something else on a tablet or phone), if the light from the computer screen is different from the color of the presentation you are showing (doing something else on the computer or playing a game), if the student does not answer the questions you ask the class, then it is very likely that the student is not focused on the lesson and is doing something else or playing a game, even though he is sitting at the computer. Show a short video related to the topic of the lesson and then

ask students questions about the topic discussed in the video to determine whether they listened to the video. Of course, a student who does not listen will not know what is being discussed in the video. We can determine the same thing by asking simple questions about the topic you are explaining and based on the answers you receive (Ismayilli, 2024). If you use presentations that alternate between light and dark slides, you can determine whether the light falling on the student's face from the computer screen matches the brightness of the slide. If the student is watching your sharing, the light falling on the student's face from the screen will also change as the light and dark slides alternate. If the student removes the slide you shared on the screen and does something else (plays a game or does other work), there will be no noticeable difference in the brightness of the light falling on the student's face from the screen, even though you change the slides. This is more noticeable during the dark hours of the day.

Nowadays, children's computer skills are not bad, but in the first lessons, students need to be taught the working principle of the program so that technical problems do not take up too much of their time later. Parents should pay attention to whether other programs are connected on the computer used by the child. At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher should announce the lesson plan, say what they will learn, and what tasks they will solve. The teacher should comment on each of his actions, especially those that are not visible on the screen. For example, "I will now show you a slide", "I am solving a problem with the camera", etc.

Intonation plays a special role in distance learning. Raising and lowering the pitch of your voice is a way to attract attention. One teacher once said to his students, "Raise your hands," and that he noticed that students who did not raise their hands were not listening to the lesson. In order to focus students' attention on the lesson in an online class, it is necessary to interest them in the lesson process. It is simply naive to expect students to listen with interest to a lecture-style lesson. To

maintain activity in the lesson, take short breaks and discuss interesting information, and do not let students get bored by organizing games for younger children and music breaks for senior students. Provide feedback. Ask questions like "Is this true or false?" and "Do you agree with these ideas or not?" and ask them to answer by putting "+" or "-" signs in the "chat" section.

It is not advisable to have a window without curtains, a cupboard with books or other items, moving, colorful objects (for example, a clock with a clock), paintings, or anything else that will attract the student's attention in the background (except for backgrounds that are relevant to the topic of the lesson). Sit in front of a solid background or use a virtual background that is relevant to the topic of the lesson. Use slides. People remember 15% of what they hear and 65% of what they see and hear at the same time. The colorfulness of the slides you show will help attract students' attention to the lesson. Online lessons give you opportunities that are not available in face-to-face lessons. Thus, it is easier to find and demonstrate materials from Internet resources that are relevant to the topic than in face-to-face lessons. Avoid extraneous sounds (echo, phone/computer notifications) (Dogan, 2025). To do this, choose a quiet place where you can't hear pets, the sound of the TV in the other room, or the conversations of people in the house. Close programs on your computer that can receive voice notifications, such as WhatsApp and Facebook Messenger. If you think that these programs may be necessary for you to communicate with students, put them on silent mode. When sharing a screen, share the slides you will be presenting, not the entire screen. Because when switching between electronic resources during the lesson, your personal information such as contacts and correspondence on your computer may appear on the students' screens.

Imagine that you have shared your entire computer screen, and then a notification with unpleasant content appears on the screen from some site or a message from an acquaintance that you do not want anyone else to know. If these notifications and messages are shared on the screens of all students' computers, at best they will distract students from the lesson. Make a video recording of the lesson. This will give students who cannot join during the lesson and do not fully understand the lesson the opportunity to watch it later. When asking questions to the class, it is better to write it in the chat section. Do not scold students who do not follow the rules in front of everyone, but warn them by writing to themselves in the "chat" section. Pay special attention to students turning their microphones on and off when necessary. The screen sharing function should be available only to you. Give each student the time they need to share their screen. Otherwise, students may accidentally share their computer screen. The content they accidentally share can ruin your entire lesson.

It is necessary to convey to students that the rules of conduct in online classes are not much different from the rules in schools. You should be polite, respect yourself and others, not offend your interlocutors, and communicate pleasantly. Let them know that following these simple rules will allow them to better absorb the material of the lessons and make the distance learning

process more efficient. Explain to students that following these rules is as necessary as following the rules of conduct in society. When starting online classes for the first time, draw up rules and discuss them with students. Be sure to take into account the opinions of students when drawing up the rules (Tünçeli, 2025). You can use the following examples when drawing up the rules. Rules for students in online classes: –Be polite. You should greet your classmates and teachers before starting the lesson, and say goodbye at the end.

Application of Web 2.0 technologies in online classes

The development of globalization processes requires certain changes in the content and organization of education. The basis of the change is the rapidly increasing flow of information. This growth is occurring at such a pace that the education system based on old methods can no longer cope with it. Increasing the volume of mastered knowledge leads to an excessive increase in the teaching load, negatively affects the health of the student, but does not give the desired results (Dash, 2024) Therefore, many experts believe that it is necessary to radically transform education, taking into account the current level of development of information technologies in connection with the processes taking place in the world. The basis of education is the interaction between people - teachers and students, as well as the students themselves

Information technology is a tool that can make this communication extremely effective. Information technology does not replace human communication - it allows you to focus on conceptual ideas by solving certain technical problems. The use of such technologies has wide possibilities.

Conclusion

The transition to online learning has fundamentally transformed the responsibilities of teachers and the structure of the teaching-learning process. Effective management of online classes requires not only subject knowledge but also strong organizational skills, technological competence, and awareness of students' digital behavior. The study shows that discipline in online classes is best achieved through clear expectations, consistent teacher behavior, and respectful communication rather than punishment. Techniques such as using varied intonation, visual materials, short videos, interactive questioning, and planned micro-breaks help maintain students' attention and prevent disengagement. Ensuring a distraction-free environment, using effective backgrounds, and providing feedback through chat further support the learning process.

Web 2.0 technologies play a crucial role in enriching online lessons by enabling collaboration, creativity, and student-centered learning. These tools help teachers move beyond traditional lecture formats and offer interactive, multimodal learning experiences. The integration of Web 2.0 tools also supports the development of digital literacy, which is essential in modern education. Overall, the study concludes that successful online teaching depends on the harmonious combination of pedagogical strategies and technological tools. When used thoughtfully, these approaches enhance communi-

cation, strengthen learner motivation, and make distance education more efficient, interactive, and meaningful.

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